

Conference "Contemporary use, models and allocation of ISBN across of World"

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ISBN Assignment Process in Moldova

Biography: Renata Cozonac is a Director of ISBN, ISSN, and ISMN National Agency in the Republic of Moldova, section of the National Book Chamber of the Republic of Moldova (NBCRM). She received her master degree in Economy from Free International University of Moldova. Her recent publications include *National Bibliography of Moldova* (co-author, 1999-2018), *NBCRM: Annual report of activity* (2017), *E-Basarabiana collection* (digitized bibliophile and rare documents from XV-XX century) (2017). Her work focuses on the developing of ISBN, ISSN and ISMN system in Moldova and results are presented in the articles published in the specialized journals of the country.

Abstracts: This article describes how the publisher can apply for and obtain ISBN for publications that are within the scope of the ISBN Standard, the procedures the publisher must to follow and the legal framework that regulates publishing activity in the Republic of Moldova.

Keywords: National Book Chamber, Moldova, NBC, ISBN assignment, ISBN National Agency, ISO standard, Legal Deposit

National Book Chamber (NBC) of the Republic of Moldova was designated as ISBN National Agency in 1993, when Republic of Moldova becomes a member of ISBN network.

*The operating rules of the ISBN System in the Republic of Moldova*¹ were developed based on the Editorial Activity Law Nr 939-XIV from 20.04.2000 with subsequent modifications and additions, the policy and strategy of the International ISBN Agency, which establishes how to manage the ISBN system, and the management of the National ISBN Registry of the Republic of Moldova.

The ISBN information system in the Republic of Moldova is intended for the registration of ISBN numbers assigned to books and brochures published by Moldova's publishers, printed in the country, and abroad.

¹<http://lex.justice.md/index.php?action=view&view=doc&lang=1&id=358447>

The ISBN numbers are assigned by the NBC as the ISBN Moldova National Agency and are based on the ISO 2108:2017 "Information and Documentation - International Standard Book Number (ISBN)".

The ISBN system in the Republic of Moldova with the NBC as the ISBN Moldova National Agency is operated according to the Republic of Moldova legislation and the relevant international standard in the field (ISO 2108).

ISBNs are intended for publishers who operate in the Republic of Moldova and have completed their registration at the NBC.

ISBN assignment is chargeable according to the Payments Service Nomenclature approved by the Government Decision Nr 1311 of 12.12.2005.

In 2006, ISBN National Agency Moldova started to use the 13-digit ISBN system. In the same period, Moldova's ISBN database was established with full data records regarding publishers, contacts, ISBNs, and complete data about registered titles.

Fig. 1

"Moldova's ISBN" database, front office

Data incheierii contractului	Data atribuirii ISBN	Nr contract	Registrant Prefix Type (ISBN)	Titlu	IDNO	Address Line 1 (de iure)	Address Line 2 (de facto)	Director	Admin phone	Admin Fax	Admin email	Director adjunct / Redactor sr	Phone	Email	Contabil / secretar stiintific	Telefon
10.08.2015	01.01.1997	08-7/2015	0	Arc IP	1012620000483	str. G. Menicu 3, MD-2009, Chisnău, Moldova		Bănsă Iurie	735329	733623	info.edurazari@gmail.com	Lungu Eugen	733619	mihail1@yahoo.com	Iacob Anghel	69102408
29.09.2015	01.01.2006	09-24/2015	45	Tehnica-UTM (Universitatea Tehnică a Moldovei)	1007600001508	bd. Ștefan cel Mare 168, MD-2004, Chisnău, Moldova		Bostan Ion	237361	445303	n_radu@mail.ru	Radu Nicolae	235441	n_radu@utm.mai.md	Moscalenco Lila	445133
25.11.2015	01.01.2006	11-25/2015	46	LPS "Ion Creangă" (Universitatea Pedagogică de Stat "Ion Creangă" din Chisnău)	10076000035769	str. I. Creangă 1, MD-2009, Chisnău, Moldova		Chioșu Nicolae	240391	245140	Guzun@uvm.moldnet.md	Vizer Boris	743303	topograf_luse@yahoo.com	Reșcu Iurie	245140
28.03.2016	01.01.2006	2016/03-7	47	Editura Universul ÎS	10036000077838	str. Vlaicu Părcălab 45, MD-2012, Chisnău, Moldova		Andreev Constantin	234616	227272	ion_tmodin@yahoo.com	Știrbu Titus	237773	editura_universul@yahoo.com	Divorean Constantin	237778
26.06.2015	01.01.2006	06-11/2015	48	Institutul de Științe ale Educației	10116010001114	str. Doina 104, MD-2059, Chisnău, Moldova		Pugălița Lilia	468733	459854	iee@ise.md		400700			
31.01.2017	01.01.2008	2017/01-3	49	Camera Națională a Cărp din Republica Moldova	1006601003959	bd. Ștefan cel Mare 180, of. 202-305, MD-2004, Chisnău, Moldova		Chitroaga Valentina	295746	295680	bookchamber.md@gmail.com	Chitroaga Valentina	295657	ISBN_Moldova@mail.md	Coznac Rianata	295616
26.04.2017	01.01.2006	2017/04-1	50	US B&B (Universitatea de Stat "A. Russo" din Bălți)	1007602000972	str. Pușkin 38, MD-3121, Bălți, Moldova		Găgim Ion	23152430	23152439	rectorat@usarb.md	Moraru Anton	23152430		Harzonă Elena	23152473
31.07.2015	01.01.2009	07-21/2015	51	Pontos SRL	1004600028808	str. 31 August 1989 95, of. 204, MD-2004, Chisnău, Moldova		Romanuc Marcela	79637544	232218	editura.pontos@gmail.com	Romanuc Marcela	232218			
06.06.14	01.01.2006	10-22/2015	52	Gratema Libris SRL	10036000038636	str. București 68, of. 313, MD-2012, Chisnău, Moldova		Șarban Ion	202555	202555	gratema@moldova.cv	Balan Maria	202553	gratemalibris@gmail.com	Sârbu Ludmila	202554
34.07.2015	26.07.2011	07-18/2015	53	Tipografia Centrală, Firma Editorial-Poligrafică ÎS	1003600105690	str. Florin 1, MD-2068, Chisnău, Moldova		Sorocovici Dmiru	442143	492185	tpar@tmr.md		404252 69245795	silvia_vip@yahoo.com	Rasakozov Tatiana	493146
14.09.2015	01.08.2011	06-12/2015	54	Prut International SRL	1003600029190	str. George Enescu 6/1, MD-2064, Chisnău, Moldova	str. Alba Iulia 231 A, MD-2071, Chisnău, Moldova	Moiea Cornelu	749318	749318	prut@tmr.md	Ceța Olga	749318	gabriela.bunavina@prut.ro		751874
14.05.2014	01.01.2007	2017/05-1	55	Cozara (Cocazaru SRL)	10076000077176	str. Ștefan cel Mare, MD-3541, com. Păneascu, Orhei		Coznac Rianata	79543005	23547880	editura_cozara@mail.ru					
18.08.2015	09.08.2011	09-19/2015	56	Print-Caro SRL	10036000061749	str. Astronom N. Donici 14, MD-2049, Chisnău, Moldova	str. Mirești 22/2, MD-2049, Chisnău, Moldova	Roșca Octavian	432575		rosc@usam.md	Roșca Octavian	69220081	printcaro@gmail.com	Roșca Octavian	69220081
21.07.2015	27.06.2013	09-20/2015	57	Tipografia-Sinus SRL	10026000035029	str. Al. Lăpușeanu 2, MD-2004, Chisnău, Moldova		Soltan Ion	232352 69104435	233512	www.sinus.md	Buludov Marole	232352 79471245	sinus@sinus.md	Chiosa Ion	232951 69104435
15.07.2015	01.01.2008	07-4/2015	58	Tipografia Redama SA	10036000025616	str. Alexandru cel Bun 111, MD-2012, Chisnău, Moldova		Oprea Anastasia	227368	244615	tipografia_redama@yahoo.com		227200		243067	244615
22.07.2015	14.08.2013	07-11/2015	59	Cavaliu SRL	10086000053605	str. Doina 104, Chisnău, Moldova		Cavaliuc Valeriu	079527202	400717	valeriu@gmail.com					
14.08.2015	01.01.2010	08-10/2015	60	Epigraf SRL	1003600165114	str. Șoseavă 44/7 ap. 7, MD-2012, Chisnău, Moldova	str. București 80/11, MD-2012, Chisnău, Moldova	Bujor Oleg	228587	228587	epigraf@tmr.md		225980	epigraf_md@yahoo.com	Nica Maria	436384
26.08.2015	01.01.1996	08-21/2015	62	Tipografia A&M	10036000029698	str. Petru Movilă 8, MD-2004, Chisnău, Moldova		Schișco Valeriu	235342	235216	tesmtrn@yahoo.com		235218			
22.05.2015	01.01.1996	05-5/2015	63	Tehnica-Imb SRL	1003600129691	bd. Moscova 18, of. 35, MD-2045, Chisnău, Moldova		Marin Alexandru	321813	069075268	aman@mail.um.md	Marin Alexandru	321813	maxim_vasilenco@yahoo.com		
32.02.2009	01.01.1996	2016/03-1	64	UASM (Universitatea Agrară de Stat din Moldova)	10076000002716	str. Mirești 44, MD-2049, Chisnău, Moldova		Cimpoeș Gheorghe	022424433		cozma@usam.md	Cozma Adrian	432575	cimpoes@usam.md	Cozma Adrian	294987
						bd. Ștefan cel Mare 180, of. 505, MD-										

In accordance with the Republic of Moldova's laws to become a publisher, each legal entity must meet these requirements:

1. The legal status must include the economic classification of activity - "58.11 book publishing activities" or "18.1 printing and printing related service activities" according to NACE rev. 2 (Classification of Economic Activities in EC)²
2. To sign a contract between the legal entity and the National Book Chamber of Republic of Moldova.

²<http://www.statistica.md/pageview.php?l=en&idc=385>

Fig. 2

Become a Publisher

The National Book Chamber of Moldova is also designated as CIP agency and National Bibliographic Agency. Therefore, every publisher, upon his request to register a new title, will get the CIP, UDC, and ISBN. In Moldova, the process of obtaining the ISBN follows the model "one request - one allocated ISBN".

Upon registration, publishers receive an ISBN for each title, regardless of the number of titles / documents received each day. Publishers can apply for subsequent ISBNs through the (mandatory) confirmation of previously requested ISBNs, as required by law.

There are two ways to make a request – either in person at the NBC office or online (via email). The first variant permits two methods of payment – by cash at the NBC office or by bank transfer, the second permits just one – the bank transfer.

Fig. 3

Registration at the NBC office

Fig. 4

Online registration via email

Providing a Legal Deposit copy is mandatory and this must be presented to NBC and submitted within two months (for titles that will be printed out of the country the deadline will be extended) of assignment of the ISBN number. At the back office of the "Moldova's ISBN" database,

we have full data records of all registered titles, with blue is marked titles that NBC has not yet received as Legal Deposit.

Fig. 5

"Moldova's ISBN" database, back office for ISBN prefixes "978-9975-0"

Inventa	Data	ISBN-13	Autor		Tipografia	Tiraj
	26.12.2017	978-9975-0-0114-4	Santilan Jorge	Colorez animale : P. 1	Malaysia	3000
	26.12.2017	978-9975-0-0115-1	Santilan Jorge	Colorez animale : P. 2	Malaysia	3000
2017-2653	02.01.2018	978-9975-0-0116-8	Roşcovanu Veronica	Limba română pentru şcolile cu instruire în limba rusă : clasa a 8-a : Caietul elevului	Bons Offices	2000
2018-174	02.01.2018	978-9975-0-0117-5	Греку Мирча	В гостях у Медвежонка Марми : (сборник терапевтических сказок для детей дошкольного и младшего школьного возраста), ed. 2	Bons Offices	1000
	11.01.2018	978-9975-0-0118-2		Citeşte şi construieşte : Carte şi cuburi de construit	China	1000
2018-398	23.01.2018	978-9975-0-0119-9	Ursu Valentina	Jurnal săptămânal la europa Liberă : Partea a 13-a : dec. 2016 - dec. 2017	Bons Offices	1200
2018-390	29.01.2018	978-9975-0-0120-5	Vandebriil Michaël	New rom antics	Bons Offices	500
2018-784	02.02.2018	978-9975-0-0121-2	Mysjkin Jan H.	Poetule, piaptână-ţi părul! : Cincisprezece poezi neerlandezi	Bons Offices	500
2018-782	12.02.2018	978-9975-0-0122-9	Steele Philip	Atlasul meu geografic : conţine un poster pilot cu harta lumii	China	2000
2018-400	14.02.2018	978-9975-0-0123-6	Enciu Nicolae	1918 pe ruinele imperiului spulberat de istorie. Basarabia în pragul modernităţii	Bons Offices	300
2018-393	14.02.2018	978-9975-0-0124-3	Țurcanu Ion	Statul țării : Istoria zbuciumată a unei importante instituții politice basarabene din anii 1917-1918	Bons Offices	300
2018-579	20.02.2018	978-9975-0-0125-0	Bulat Vladimir	Forme geometrice : Un eseu despre artistul Dumitru Russu-Scvorțov și opera sa	Bons Offices	500
	26.02.2018	978-9975-0-0126-7	Cojocar Dragoș	Cartea mea de magie	China	2000
	26.02.2018	978-9975-0-0127-4	Seria	Biblioteca creativă		
2018-793	15.03.2018	978-9975-0-0128-1	Ciubotaru Mihail Ion	Temerea de obișnuință	Bons Offices	500
	16.03.2018	978-9975-0-0129-8	Secieru Rodica	Republica Moldova. Curtea Constituțională. Raport privind exercitarea jurisdicției constituționale în anul 2017	Europes	200
	21.03.2018	978-9975-0-0130-4	Bulat Nicolae	De la sațră la palat	Ungaria	1000
2018-794	29.03.2018	978-9975-0-0131-1	Meniuc George	Pe rug fiecare devine liber	Bons Offices	500
	03.04.2018	978-9975-0-0132-8	Brizzolara Chiara	Fashion girl : Cum să fi o fată la modă	Ungaria	4000
2018-783	05.04.2018	978-9975-0-0133-5	Ungureanu Mihai	Să cânte părinți, să cânte copii : Culegere de cântece pentru toate vârstele	Bons Offices	1000
2018-838	05.04.2018	978-9975-0-0134-2	Velișco Nadejda	Chimie : Teste preparatorii pentru examenul de bacalaureat : (profil real, profilurile umanistic, arte, sport)	Bons Offices	2000
2017-798	05.04.2018	978-9975-0-0135-9	Велишко Надежда	Химия : Тесты для подготовки к экзамену на степень бакалавра : (профили: реальный, гуманитарный, искусство, спорт)	Bons Offices	2000
	06.04.2018	978-9975-0-0136-6	Botnaru Vasile	DesCântece pentru vin : Microantologie cu oenograme	Ungaria	1100
2018-799	11.04.2018	978-9975-0-0137-3	Lungu Svetlana	English-Speaking Countries : Culture and Civilization Topics for the Baccalaureate Exam	Bons Offices	3000

Thanks to this model of ISBN allocation, we have achieved outstanding results in the editorial-publishing field:

- The Legal Deposit in Moldova covers 98% of all published documents;
- The illegal use of ISBNs has been excluded (duplication, erroneous writing);
- Quick possibility of identifying the author-title-ISBN relationship;
- Exemption from VAT on the basis of the systematization certificate issued by the NBC.

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4. *The Fiscal code of the Republic of Moldova, Title III "Value Added Tax", art. 103.* Available online at: <http://lex.justice.md/md/326971/> (accessed on September 18. 2018)